

Effect of Cement Type on Alkali Silica Reactivity of Coarse Aggregates

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Abstract

The alkali-silica reaction (ASR) is a harmful interaction between alkaline cement paste and reactive silica in concrete aggregates, forming an expansive gel that can cause cracking and shorten the lifespan of the concrete structure. This research study examines the ASR phenomenon in local coarse aggregate with ordinary Portland cement (OPC) and sulfate-resistant cement (SRC). After 3, 7, 14, and 28 days, the 24 mortar prism samples underwent an ASTM C1260 expansion test. The results indicated that the OPC bars expanded by 0.192% to 0.48%, and the SRC bars expanded by 0.270% to 0.464%. Expansion after 14 days $> 0.2\%$ is considered high reactivity, and both cements exhibited this, indicating that the local aggregates are highly reactive per ASTM C1260. After 28 days, the SRC's performance was slightly better. The study suggests using low-alkali cement, pozzolanic materials, moisture control, and nonreactive aggregates to minimize ASR effects.

Keywords: *Alkali-silica reaction (ASR), Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), Sulfate-resistant cement (SRC), ASTM C1260, Coarse aggregate reactivity.*

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Introduction

The most common building material worldwide since the early 19th century, concrete is a mixture of binder (cement and lime), water, aggregates, and other additives (admixtures) that impart specific properties (Makul, 2021; Surahyo et al., 2019). While early concrete's effectiveness and durability initially garnered significant popularity, it was later determined that concrete structures could deteriorate over time, affecting their longevity and functionality (Aslam et al., 2026; Ma et al., 2025). Researchers have conducted extensive research, and it has been established that one of the major

causes of concrete deterioration is alkali-silica reaction (ASR) (Aslani et al., 2023; Azam et al., 2023). ASR occurs between the alkali metals in the cement and the silicates in the aggregates. When ASR occurs, a significant portion of concrete is susceptible to deterioration because aggregate accounts for about one-third of the concrete's total volume (HO, 2024; Tapas, 2020). Hence, it is essential to characterize the aggregates chemically and physically before their application in the concrete mix (Evangelista et al., 2015).

In some of the most commonly used aggregates, reactive amorphous silica can combine with the very alkaline cement paste, leading to harmful swelling (ASR, or concrete cancer) over time in the presence of sufficient moisture (Olajide et al., 2023). It forms an alkali-silica gel that absorbs water from the surrounding paste, causing the paste to expand. This expansion puts pressure on the concrete's interior, causing microcracks when the pressure exceeds the concrete's tensile strength (Allford, 2016; Asmara, 2023). ASR is a localized reaction, and the severity of deterioration can vary across different areas of the same structure depending on the composition of the pore solution, the characteristics of the reactive aggregate particles, and the structure's configuration (Sanchez et al., 2025; Zapala-Slaweta, 2023). Three conditions must be met for deleterious ASR to occur: a high concentration of hydroxyl ions in the pore solution, the presence of a reactive siliceous aggregate, and access to moisture (Olajide et al., 2022).

The structural effects of ASR on concrete include unwanted expansion, decreases in compressive strength, large losses of tensile strength and flexural capacity (up to 85% in some bridge structures), reductions in moduli of elasticity, decreases in fatigue life, and alterations in shear strength (Cao, 2021). The design life of a 100-year-old building can be shortened to 30-40 years by implementing active ASR (Brueckner et al., 2024; Furgani & Chesterton, 2024).

The research aims to investigate the ASR of local coarse aggregates using two types of cement (OPC and SRC). The aim is to obtain the results of the accelerated mortar bar test method (ASTM C1260) for coarse aggregates using both cement types and to provide recommendations based on the results.

Experimental Program

Raw Materials

In this study, two types of cement were used: ordinary Portland cement (OPC, Type I, Grade 53) and sulfate-resistant cement (SRC) conforming to ASTM C150. OPC is the most used cement in construction, and SRC contains less than 5% tricalcium aluminate, which makes it resistant to sulfate attack in underwater and other aggressive environments. Both the cements were bought from the city of Nawabshah with the brand name Lucky Cement. The physical and chemical properties of OPC and SRC are given in Tables 1 and 2. The coarse aggregate was taken from a local site in Nawabshah (Kumar et al., 2023). Distilled water was used to avoid interfering side reactions that might occur during hydration. The coarse aggregate was first washed extensively with clean water to remove dust, clay, and organic matter (A Kumar et al., 2024; Ajay Kumar et al., 2024). The aggregate was washed and then dried on the ground. The aggregate was then dried and ground into powder in the Los Angeles abrasion machine, which imposes hard abrasion, impact, and grinding by hardened steel balls. The ground particles were then sieved through various sieve sizes to obtain the desired grading, as per Table 3. The grading criteria specified mass percentages to be retained on sieve Nos. To obtain uniformity and consistency, 8, 16, 30, 50, and 100 were used for all the mortar prisms. In general, Fig. 1 shows that the raw material collection process is systematic, and the L.A. abrasion process is important for obtaining fine-aggregate powder for cement-based composites.

Table 1. Physical Properties of OPC and SRC

Physical properties		OPC	SRC
Unit weight	(g/cm ³)	3.16	3.22
Fineness	Surface area (cm ² /g)	3310	3210
Setting time	Initial (h-min)	2-20	3-10
	Final (h-min)	3-30	4-40
Compressive strength (kg/cm ²)	3 days	291	219
	7 days	440	314
	28 days	613	508
Heat of hydration (J/g)	7 days	330	276
	28 days	375	322

Table 2. Chemical Composition of OPC and SRC

Chemical compound	Loss on ignition (LOI)	Magnesium oxide (MgO)	Sulfur trioxide (SO ₃)	Chloride ion (Cl ⁻)	Sodium oxide (Na ₂ O)	Tricalcium silicate (C ₃ S)	Dicalcium silicate (C ₂ S)	Tricalcium aluminate (C ₃ A)	Tetracalcium alumina (C ₄ AF)
OPC	1.96	1.49	2.06	0.008	0.58	52	22	9	9
SRC	0.90	0.80	2.00	0.002	0.55	54	23	3	14

Figure 1. Schematic Representation of the Sample Preparation Process for Cement-Mortar Incorporating Coarse Aggregate Powder Derived from Los Angeles Abrasion

Table 3. Grading Requirements for Aggregate Powder (ASTM C1260)

Sieve No.	Sieve Opening (mm)	Passing (%)	Retained on	Mass Retained (%)
8	2.36	100	No. 16	10
16	1.18	90	No. 30	25
30	0.600	65	No. 50	25
50	0.300	40	No. 100	25
100	0.150	15	Pan	15

Note: Total mass of aggregate powder per batch = 900 g. Percentages refer to mass retained on each successive sieve.

Preparation and Testing Methods

A total of 24 mortar prisms were prepared, each measuring 11" × 1" × 1" (280 mm × 25 mm × 25 mm). The OPC was used to cast 12 prisms, and the SRC was used to cast 12 prisms. All the prisms were cast and then cured in distilled water for 28 days. Expansion measurements were taken on these cures at 3, 7, 14, and 28 days. At each time interval, three prisms of each cement type were tested. The ingredients of the mortar mix are given in Table 2. Mortar bar expansion tests were carried out following the ASTM C227 procedure. The bars were kept in water at 38°C to facilitate their expansion. Each prism was expanded using a length-comparator apparatus comprising a sensitive indicator attached to a dual-post frame, on which moving and resting anvils are mounted. The process of preparation of aggregate and testing is explained in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Experimental Design for Evaluating Length Change in OPC and SRC Mortars - from Raw Material Processing to Periodic Measurement

Table 2. Mortar Mix Design

Materials	Cement	Aggregate powder	Water
Values in Kg/m ³	533	1200	250

Results and Discussion

Expansion Behavior of OPC and SRC Mortar Bars

The results of the expansion measurements showed that the type of cement significantly affects ASR-induced expansion. For OPC mortar bars, the average expansion values were 0.192% at 3 days, 0.304% at 7 days, 0.405% at 14 days, and 0.480% at 28 days. This gradual rise indicates that the alkali-silica reaction begins early in the life of the concrete and continues as the concrete ages, with the gel absorbing moisture and swelling. Interestingly, the 7-day expansion (0.304%) exceeded the 0.2% limit set by ASTM C1260 for reactive aggregates. The expansion pattern of mortar bars (SRC), however, was different. At 3 days, SRC showed greater expansion (0.270%) than OPC (0.192%). However, at 28 days, SRC growth (0.464%) was marginally lower than OPC's (0.480%). It indicates that in later ages, the presence of SRC would inhibit the development of ASR, possibly

because of its low tricalcium aluminate content (less than 5%), which reduces the alkali available for the reaction. However, all the SRC expansion values at 7, 14, and 28 days (0.377%, 0.441%, and 0.464%, respectively) were above 0.2%, indicating that the local aggregate is very reactive, irrespective of the type of cement used, with only marginal improvement at later ages with SRC. The expansion data are summarized in Table 3 and plotted in Fig. 3 for both cement types at different testing ages.

Table 3. Expansion Results of OPC and SRC Mortar Bars at Different Ages

Age (days)	Average expansion of OPC (%)	Average expansion of SRC (%)	Difference (%)
3	0.192	0.270	+0.078 (SRC higher)
7	0.304	0.377	+0.073 (SRC higher)
14	0.405	0.441	+0.036 (SRC higher)
28	0.480	0.464	-0.016 (OPC higher)

Figure 3. Comparative Expansion of OPC and SRC Mortar Bars at Each Age

ASR Reactivity Classification

The acceptance criteria for ASTM C1260 mortar bar test define that when the expansion is less than 0.1% after 14 days, the aggregate is non-reactive; when the expansion is between 0.1% and 0.2% after 14 days, the aggregate is slowly reactive; and when the expansion is more than 0.2% after 14 days, the aggregate is highly reactive. The expansion of OPC bars and SRC bars in this study was 0.405% and 0.441%, respectively, both exceeding the 0.2% limit. Thus, the coarse aggregate used in Nawabshah is highly reactive to alkali-silica reaction. This finding is consistent with the observations of Munir et al. (Munir, 2016), who reported that aggregates sourced from the mountainous regions of Pakistan exhibit a high potential for alkali-silica reactivity, attributed to their siliceous mineral composition.

Time-Dependent Expansion Progression

The rate of expansion over time provides clues to the kinetics of ASR. For OPC bars, expansion increased by approximately 58% from 3 days (0.192%) to 7 days (0.304%), then by 33% from 7 days to 14 days (0.405%). After 14 days, the expansion continued to increase, albeit at a slower

rate, reaching 0.480% at 28 days. This means that the fastest rate of ASR growth is during the first 14 days of accelerated testing. For SRC bars, expansion increased by approximately 40% from 3 days (0.270%) to 7 days (0.377%), then by 17% to 14 days (0.441%), and only by 5% from 14 to 28 days (0.464%). However, the significantly lower expansion rate after 14 days for SRC (Table 4 and Fig. 4) indicates that the ASR expansion rate is partly suppressed in mixes containing SRC. This is probably due to the reduced alkali content available for reaction and the denser structure of the sulfate-resisting cement. The expansion rates (slope) between measurement intervals are shown in Table 4. The rate for OPC decreased from 0.0640 %/day (0-3 days) to 0.0054 %/day (14-28 days), while the rate for SRC decreased from 0.0900 %/day to 0.0016 %/day over the same periods. SRC performance is consistently lower after 7 days, further confirming its relatively better performance at later ages.

Figure 4. Expansion Rate Progression of OPC and SRC Mortar Bars

Table 4. Data for the Expansion Rate (Slope) between Intervals

Interval (days)	OPC Expansion Increase (%)	SRC Expansion Increase (%)	OPC Rate (%/day)	SRC Rate (%/day)
0-3	0.192	0.270	0.0640	0.0900
3-7	0.112	0.107	0.0280	0.0268
7-14	0.101	0.064	0.0144	0.0091
14-28	0.075	0.023	0.0054	0.0016

Conclusions

The study used locally available coarse aggregates to investigate the Alkali-Silica Reaction (ASR) in Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) and Sulfate-Resisting Cement (SRC). The twenty-four mortar prisms were tested in accordance with ASTM C1260, and expansion measurements were recorded at 3, 7, 14, and 28 days. The locally available coarse aggregate is highly reactive, as both cement types exhibited expansions > 0.2% at 14 days (OPC: 0.405%, SRC: 0.441%). The expansion of OPC bars at 3 days rose from 0.192% to 0.48% at 28 days. For SRC bars, expansion increased from 0.270% at 3 days to 0.464% at 28 days. At 28 days, SRC expansion was slightly lower than that of OPC, but it remained highly reactive. The use of such aggregates poses a significant risk of

premature deterioration of the concrete structure. With active ASR, a 100-year-old building will only last 30-40 years.

Suggestions

To minimize alkali-aggregate reaction in local aggregates, use low-alkali cement and silica fume/fly ash as pozzolanic admixtures. Keep moisture out and maintain in-house RH levels < 80%. Use non-reactive aggregates or substitute 30% crushed limestone. Apply a low water-cement ratio, lithium salts, air-entrainment, and regular cleaning of structures.

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